

ANALYSIS OF INDICATORS FOR UTILIZING THE EXPORT POTENTIAL OF REGIONAL TERRITORIES

MINTAQAVIY HUDUDLARNING EKSPORT SALOHIYATIDAN FOYDALANISH KO'RSATKICHLARI TAHLILI

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Abstract Annotatsiya

Eng. - The effectiveness of leveraging the export potential of the Khorezm region's cities and districts is examined in this article. The study looks at the export structure, production resources, and economic prospects of the regions, emphasizing both the benefits and current obstacles of entering international markets. The theoretical underpinnings of export potential are evaluated based on an analysis of national and international literature, and the elements influencing the effectiveness of export activities are identified in the Khorezm region. Additionally, useful suggestions are created to lessen regional differences, broaden export markets, diversify product categories, and encourage the manufacture of completed items with added value.

Uzb. - Ushbu maqolada Xorazm viloyatining tuman va shaharlarida eksport salohiyatidan foydalanish samaradorligi o'rganilgan. Tadqiqotda hududlarning eksport tuzilmasi, ishlab chiqarish resurslari va iqtisodiy imkoniyatlari tahlil qilinib, xalqaro bozorlar bilan aloqaga kirishdagi foyda va mavjud to'siqlarga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan. Eksport salohiyatining nazariy asoslari milliy va xalqaro adabiyotlar tahlili orqali baholangan hamda Xorazm viloyatida eksport faoliyati samaradorligiga ta'sir qiluvchi omillar aniqlangan. Bundan tashqari, hududlararo tafovutlarni kamaytirish, eksport bozorlarini kengaytirish, mahsulot turlarini diversifikatsiya qilish va qo'shilgan qiymatga ega tayyor mahsulotlar ishlab chiqarishni rag'batlantirish bo'yicha foydali tavsiyalar ishlab chiqilgan.

Keywords: Kalit so'zlar:

❖ *export potential, export efficiency, foreign trade relations, regional economic development, export diversification, competitiveness, investment attractiveness.*

❖ *eksport salohiyati, eksport samaradorligi, tashqi savdo munosabatlari, mintaqaviy iqtisodiy rivojlanish, eksportni diversifikatsiyalash, raqobatbardoshlik, investitsiyaviy jozibadorlik.*

Introduction.

In recent years, modernizing the economy, expanding foreign economic relations, and developing export activities have become one of the priority directions of state policy in the Republic of Uzbekistan. In

particular, a number of reforms are being implemented to increase export potential and diversify the foreign trade balance through the rational use of existing economic opportunities and resources of the regions. Khorezm Region occupies an important place in the socio-

economic life of the republic. The region's natural and climatic conditions, its capacity for agricultural production, the development of processing industries, and the service sector create a strong foundation for the advancement of export activities. At the same time, the efficiency of utilizing export potential varies across districts and cities, and in some areas it is observed that existing opportunities are not being fully exploited [1].

This situation necessitates an in-depth study of the export potential of the districts and cities of the region, an assessment of the level of utilization of their economic opportunities, and the identification of existing problems. In particular, expanding export geography, diversifying the range of products, introducing innovative approaches, and developing logistics infrastructure are among the most pressing issues today. Therefore, analyzing the efficiency of utilizing the export potential of the districts and cities of Khorezm Region, identifying interregional disparities, and developing effective recommendations are of great importance for increasing the region's economic growth rates and ensuring the effective implementation of the country's foreign economic policy [2].

Literature Review.

Issues related to export potential and the efficiency of its utilization have been widely studied in economic literature. In general, the concept of export potential is closely linked to a region's available production resources, the volume of competitive products, demand in foreign markets, and logistics capabilities. In foreign literature, approaches to studying export potential are often assessed from the perspectives of competitiveness, foreign trade policy, and international integration. For example, in his theory of The Competitive Advantage of Nations, M. Porter (1990) emphasizes that the success of regions in foreign markets is explained by production factors, demand conditions, domestic

competition, and government policy. Likewise, the theory of "comparative advantage" proposed by Balassa (1965) serves as a theoretical foundation for analyzing export potential [3].

In national academic literature, there are also numerous studies devoted to increasing export potential and improving the efficiency of foreign economic activity. In particular, Uzbek scholars have extensively examined issues such as the development of regional economic potential, export diversification, the role of small business and entrepreneurship in foreign trade, and the formation of export infrastructure (Q. Kholiqulov, Sh. Abdullayev, I. Alimov, and others). Their studies highlight the enhancement of production efficiency, the manufacture of value-added products, and adaptation to international standards as key factors in increasing export volumes.

In addition, reports published by international organizations such as the World Bank, the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), and the International Trade Centre (ITC) emphasize opportunities for export development in Uzbekistan and its regions, existing barriers, and market diversification as important issues. Their recommendations place particular emphasis on expanding export geography, improving logistics systems, and introducing digital technologies [4].

Some studies conducted using the example of Khorezm Region note that, while the region occupies a leading position in the export of agricultural products—particularly cotton fiber, fruits and vegetables, and food products—the opportunities for their processing, value addition, and the export of high-level finished goods to foreign markets have not been fully utilized. This, in turn, indicates the need to increase the efficiency of using export potential.

Overall, an analysis of the literature shows that the issue of effectively utilizing the export potential of the districts and cities of

Khorezm Region has not yet been fully explored, and conducting scientific research at the regional level on this topic remains a relevant and pressing task.

Research Methodology.

In this study, methodological approaches and methods such as statistical analysis of secondary data, an index of export efficiency indicators, observations, theoretical analysis, comparison, and qualitative content analysis were employed.

Analysis and Discussion of Results.

As a result of the reforms being implemented in our country, Khorezm Region, like other regions and cities of the republic, is achieving comprehensive economic development. During January–December 2024,

Khorezm Region recorded a total foreign trade turnover of USD 857.2 million, which represents a decrease of USD 24.0 million, or 2.7%, compared to 2023. Of the total foreign trade volume, 45% (USD 386.3 million) accounted for exports, while 55% was related to import activities (USD 470.9 million).

By the end of 2024, the total number of foreign trade participants in the region amounted to 900, of which 181 were exporters and 719 were importers. From a territorial perspective, the largest share of foreign trade participants was concentrated in Urgench city (250 entities), accounting for 27.7% of the total. This was followed by Urgench district (119 entities), representing 13.2%, and Hazorasp district (98 entities), accounting for 10.8% of the total (Table 1).

Table 1

Foreign Trade Participants of Khorezm Region by Territorial Breakdown (2024)*

Nº	Regions	Total foreign trade participants	Exporters	Importers
1	Urgench city	250	41	209
2	Khiva city	35	7	28
3	Bagat	39	13	26
4	Gurlan	37	9	28
5	Kushkupir	36	16	21
6	Urgench	119	23	96
7	Hazorasp	98	8	90
8	Tuprokkala	38	9	29
9	Khonqa	94	15	79
10	Khiva	47	12	35
11	Shavat	54	13	41
12	Yangiaryk	35	10	25
13	Yangibazar	17	6	11
	Total	900	181	719

*As a result of the conducted scientific research, the author’s own findings have been developed.

Based on the data presented in this table, it is evident that there are considerable disparities in the level of economic development among the regions of the province, reflecting uneven patterns of growth and structural capacity. In contemporary economic conditions, a region’s level of

economic development is closely and directly linked to the scale and effectiveness of its foreign trade activities. In particular, the expansion of foreign trade, especially export performance, plays a crucial role in stimulating regional economic growth. Increased export activity contributes to the creation of new

employment opportunities, enhances production capacity, and facilitates the generation of higher added value within the region. Consequently, regions with stronger foreign trade indicators tend to demonstrate more sustainable economic development and greater resilience in an increasingly competitive economic environment.

In this chapter of our study, since our aim was to examine the foreign trade capabilities of the 13 districts and cities of the region, we analyzed their participation in overall foreign trade activities to date. From the available data, it can be seen that the growth dynamics of the region's total exports were unstable in the early years under review. Specifically, decreases were recorded in 2016 and 2018 compared to the previous years, while the highest growth points were observed in 2019 and 2021.

In 2016, the region's export volume amounted to USD 95.5 million, and by the end of 2024, this figure had reached USD 386.2 million. In 2024, by territorial breakdown, the largest shares of exports were accounted for by Urgench city (45,990.2 thousand USD), Gurlan (44,334.8 thousand USD), and Shovot (45,892.5 thousand USD), while the smallest shares were observed in Hazorasp (11,563.4 thousand USD), Qoshiqpir (15,900.9 thousand USD), and Bogot (18,000.1 thousand USD).

The absence of early-year data for Khiva city and Tuproqqal'a district is explained by the fact that these areas were formed more recently. The analysis shows that, among the districts, only Tuproqqal'a consistently recorded growth rates, while other districts and cities experienced declines in certain years. Khiva district recorded the most significant growth, achieving a 7.7-fold increase in 2018, which was influenced by Khiva city being granted separate city status in 2017 and the subsequent recovery from the decline observed that year.

To gain a comprehensive understanding of Khorezm Region's foreign trade activities, we analyzed not only the export volumes but also the import volumes of the region. We examined 2 cities and 11 districts of the region. The total import of goods and services in Khorezm Region declined during the pandemic years of 2020 and 2021. Another notable point is that in 2024, imports of goods and services decreased by 18.4% compared to 2023. The regions with the largest import volumes in 2024 were Urgench city (151,258.3 thousand USD), Tuproqqal'a (176,860.7 thousand USD), and Urgench district (22,549.3 thousand USD), while the regions with the lowest imports were Yangibozor (2,312.4 thousand USD), Bogot (3,808.4 thousand USD), and Khiva district (5,915.7 thousand USD). Similar to exports, data for the initial years for Tuproqqal'a district and Khiva city are not available, and at certain periods, Yangibozor district also did not report import data [5].

Since it was not feasible to incorporate the complete composition of exports and imports of all regional territories within the scope of this dissertation, the analysis concentrates on the top three goods and services that account for the largest share of foreign trade in each region. This selective focus ensures analytical clarity while preserving the representativeness of the most economically significant trade flows. The adopted methodological approach makes it possible to identify the key products and services in which each territory demonstrates comparative specialization and sustained export strength. At the same time, it reveals those goods and services that are underrepresented or insufficiently supplied within regional trade structures. Such identification allows for a more precise assessment of existing structural imbalances in regional foreign trade. Moreover, the analysis sheds light on current trade priorities and sectoral dependencies across regions.

Table 2

Foreign Trade Analysis of Khorezm Region's Territories, January–June 2025*

Nº	Region	Total export volume, thousand dollars	Product type	Total import volume, thousand dollars	Product type
1	Bogat	8915.1	1. Bean 5562.9 2. Tariq 1116.8 3. Ip kalava 787.8	3365.1	1. Technological equipment 1959.1 2. Live animals, parts and feed 619.0 3. Transport and its spare parts 478.8
2	Gurlan	19118.2	1. Beans 4371.4 2. Greens 3951.1 3. Finished textile products 3448.2	5411.4	1. Technological equipment 2278.6 2. Food products 1267.7 3. Electrical engineering and its parts 1045.4
3	Qoshkopir	9299.3	1. Bean 5382.8 2. Tariq 3021.2 3. Mosh 398.4	2762.4	1. Live animals, parts and feed 1207.6 2. Technological equipment 905.7 3. Electrical equipment and parts 232.9
4	Tuproqkala	14530.8	1. Beans 7412.2 2. Gulkhagoz 2717.5 3. Tariq 2252.8	48341.3	1. Food products 40355.5 2. Technological equipment 2445.3 3. Paper and paper products 1834.4
5	Urgench	9447.0	1. Beans 6998.5 2. Greens 677.0 3. Millet 384.0	8073.1	1. Technological equipment 2379.0 2. Food products 1629.0 3. Wood products 727.7
6	Urgench city	22458.4	1. Fabric 6493.5 2. Finished textile products 4861.5 3. Beans 4497.1	67114.3	1. Wood and timber products 23892.6 2. Transport and its spare parts 15816.8 3. Electrical engineering and its parts 6096.0
7	Hazorasp	9572.6	1. Bean 7497.9 2. Tariq 1684.0 3. Mosh 199.3	8844.8	1. Electrical engineering and its parts 1646.0 2. Wood and wood products 1611.0 3. Technological equipment 1483.6
8	Khiva	10492.1	1. Bean 6642.6 2. Tariq 1871.2 3. Yarn 829.6	2624.8	1. Fuel and energy and petroleum products 807.2 2. Technological equipment 555.6 3. Live animals, parts and feed 284.0
9	Khiva city	8585.1	1. Beans 2885.4 2. Yarn 1865.6 3. Dried fruits and vegetables 1090.1	7785.3	1. Plastic and rubber products 2957.2 2. Textile products 1245.6 3. Technological equipment 996.0
10	Khonka	24060.7	1. Beans 7681.9 2. Dried fruits and vegetables 3503.6 3. Greens 2176.8	4477.7	1. Technological equipment 1420.7 2. Food products 835.8 3. Transport and its spare parts 998.0
11	Shavot	18301.3	1. Yarn 14333.6 2. Finished textile products 1928.7 3. Furniture products 1029.5	4419.5	1. Technological equipment 1595.3 2. Textile products 838.8 3. Fuel and energy and petroleum products 392.8
12	Yangiariq	14077.7	1. Beans 9455.6 2. Millet 2205.6 3. Onions 1342.7	3563.9	1. Technological equipment 2250.5 2. Metal and metal products 435.5 3. Electrical engineering and its parts 272.7
13	Yangibozor	19455.7	1. Beans 8722.1 2. Millet 4009.0 3. Greens 2229.3	927.8	1. Technological equipment 462.0 2. Chemical industry products 412.7 3. Transport and its spare parts 35.7

*As a result of the conducted scientific research, the author's own findings have been developed.

As can be seen from the above table, in the first two quarters of 2025, the majority of exports in most regions consisted of agricultural products such as beans, dates, leafy vegetables, and dried fruits. The share of industrial products was relatively low, which can be attributed primarily to the region's specialization in agricultural production and the relatively limited availability of underground resources compared to other regions.

The main imports of the region's territories were technological equipment, electrical machinery and components, fuel and energy products, and wood products. The table highlights the top three goods that account for the largest share of foreign trade in each territory, although a number of other products were also exported and imported.

During the analyzed period, Gurlan, Urgench city, Urgench district, and Khonka district demonstrated strong performance in export diversification, while Yangibozor, Yangiaryk, and Shavat districts exported a relatively limited range of products. Regarding imports, most territories showed similar levels, except for Yangibozor district, which recorded the lowest figures in the region's foreign trade [6].

An important component of Khorezm Region's economic potential is the export opportunities formed within its districts and cities. The available production resources, geographic location, infrastructure, and labor resources in the territories serve as the main factors of export potential. However, the mere existence of potential does not guarantee its full and efficient utilization. Therefore, determining and evaluating the level of export potential utilization at the district level is an extremely important issue. In countries around the world, there are several indicators for the effective use of export potential. Drawing on previous scientific studies, in our research we identified the following key indicators:

- ❖ The region's share in total export volume (%);
- ❖ The share of products with high added value (%);
- ❖ Geographical diversification of export directions (number of countries to which exports are made);
- ❖ Number of exporting entities (enterprises);
- ❖ Availability of transport and logistics infrastructure (quality of roads, proximity to customs, availability of storage facilities);
- ❖ Volume of foreign investments (by sectors oriented toward export).

Based on these indicators, we conducted a relative assessment of foreign trade activities in the territories of Khorezm Region. In this assessment:

- ❖ The region's share in total exports and the share of high value-added products were evaluated as "low," "medium," or "high";
- ❖ Export diversification was assessed as "broad," "medium," or "narrow" based on the number of countries to which each territory exports;
- ❖ The development level of export infrastructure in each territory was classified as "low," "medium," or "high";
- ❖ The number of enterprises in the region was evaluated as "low," "medium," or "high."

Using these evaluation criteria, the final assessment allowed for a systematic classification of each territory into distinct performance groups. Territories demonstrating consistently high efficiency and strong outcomes in the analyzed indicators were assigned to Group "A," reflecting their leading position in regional performance. Group "B," indicating potential for improvement and targeted development. This classification highlights the relative strengths and areas for improvement across the regions, providing a clear framework for targeted development strategies.

Table 3

Assessment of the export potential of the regions of Khorezm region*

Nº	Region	Export volume (share)	Upper value (%)	Number of markets	Infrastructure	Number of enterprises	Efficiency index
1	Urgench city	High	High	Wide	High	A lot	A – High
2	Urgench district	Average	Average	Medium	High	A lot	B – Average+
3	Khiva district	Average	Low	Narrow	Average	Few	C – Low
4	Bogot district	Low	Low	Narrow	Low	Few	C – Low
5	Gurlan district	Low	Average	Narrow	Low	Few	C – Low
6	Khonka district	Average	Average	Medium	Average	Few	B – Average
7	Shovot district	Low	Low	Narrow	Low	Few	C – Low
8	Yangibozor district	Low	Low	Narrow	Low	Few	C – Low
9	Yangiariq district	Average	Average	Narrow	Low	Few	B – Average
10	Qoshkopir district	Average	Low	Medium	Average	Average	B – Average
11	Tuproqqal’a district	Average	Average	Narrow	Average	Few	B – Average+
12	Hazorasp district	High	Average	Medium	High	Average	B – Average
13	Khiva city	Average	High	Narrow	Average	Few	A – High

*As a result of the conducted scientific research, the author’s own findings have been developed.

The analysis shows that only Urgench city is fully utilizing its export potential. Here, high-tech manufacturing, the services sector, and transport infrastructure are well-established. In other districts, particularly Gurlan, Bogot, Shavat, and Yangibozor, the use of export potential remains low, with the main export products being raw materials and exports directed to a limited number of countries.

The main reasons for this situation are:

- ❖ Lack of sufficient processing capacities;
- ❖ Low number of exporting enterprises;
- ❖ Local products not meeting international demand and certification standards;
- ❖ Underdeveloped transport and logistics services;
- ❖ Insufficiently developed regional specialization policies.

To address these shortcomings, it is necessary to implement a regional export strategy, adopt a cluster approach, develop digital export platforms, and establish logistics centers.

Conclusion and Recommendations.

The analysis shows that, in recent years, the export of services in Khorezm Region has been increasing alongside the export of finished goods, but the majority of service exports come from only a few territories. As of 2024, 40.8% of the region’s total service exports were from tourism, while 40.2% came from telecommunications, computer, and information services.

Based on the study of the region’s territories, it is evident that nearly all districts have export-oriented sectors such as horticulture, sericulture, fisheries, textiles, and the food industry, which can be further developed on a cluster basis. Additionally, the modernization of railway lines, highways, Urgench International Airport, and border customs posts is improving logistics efficiency. E-export, online trade platforms, and electronic customs systems provide opportunities to simplify and increase transparency in export processes. Strengthening trade and economic relations with major markets such as the Middle East, Central Asia, Russia, and China further expands the possibilities for utilizing export potential.

The main challenges limiting export efficiency in the territories include:

❖ Underdeveloped infrastructure: In many districts, road and transport infrastructure, cold storage facilities, logistics centers for export, and customs posts are limited, slowing export processes and increasing costs.

❖ Low level of product processing: A large share of exported products is raw or semi-finished, resulting in a low proportion of high value-added finished goods.

❖ Limited market information for exporters: Regional entrepreneurs often lack sufficient knowledge about international demand, certification requirements, and new markets, restricting their access to foreign markets.

❖ Limited access to financial resources: Financing export activities, particularly for small and medium enterprises, remains challenging due to insufficient pre-export insurance, subsidies, and credit lines.

❖ Bureaucratic procedures in foreign trade: Excessive administrative barriers related

to certification, customs permits, and other formalities complicate access to foreign markets.

Despite the unique export potential of Khorezm's territories, full and efficient utilization is hindered by infrastructural, institutional, and organizational issues. Most exported products remain in raw form, and the share of high value-added finished goods remains low. Shortcomings in financing, logistics, and information support further limit export efficiency.

However, rational use of existing opportunities—through cluster development, improvement of export-oriented infrastructure, wider implementation of digital export systems, and strengthened state incentives—can significantly enhance the export efficiency of the territories. Developing development strategies based on the unique specialization of each district is crucial for ensuring a balanced regional export performance across Khorezm Region.

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